

(CASE REPORT)

Ayurvedic management of ulcerative colitis: A case report

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Abstract

Ulcerative colitis is a chronic inflammatory condition in which patients show altered bowel habit such as diarrhoea, constipation, rectal bleeding, tenesmus, passage of mucous and crampy abdominal pain etc. These symptoms may be relapsing and remitting episodes of inflammation limited to the muscles layer of colon. In Ayurveda Pittaja Grahani shows symptoms having resemblance with Ulcerative colitis. Ayurveda described various treatment modalities for the management of Ulcerative colitis such as Matra Basti, Ksheer Basti, Samshaman yogas, proper nutritional supplements, herbal therapy, Yoga and meditation etc. In present study, A diagnosed case of ulcerative colitis, age 14yrs male from khushinagar Gorakhpur, came to OPD of Kayachikitsa, Guru Gorakshnath Institute of medical science, Gorakhpur. He complained bleeding per rectum, Stools with blood during defecation. Associated with fresh bleeding after defecation, since 8 months, weight loss 6-7 kgs in 6 months. He was given Matra Basti and ksheera Basti along with some drugs and his complaints not only relieved delayed remission as well. The goals of the treatment are to improve quality of life, minimize the risk of colon cancer and achieve steroids free remission of the disease ulcerative colitis.

Keywords: Pittaja Grahani; Ulcerative Collitis; Basti; Digestion; Ayurveda; Dhatvagani

1. Introduction

Ulcerative colitis is a cause of significant morbidity worldwide and its incidence [1] and prevalence appear to be increasing day by day. Its incidence is rising especially in Northern India, due to erroneous dietary habits and faulty lifestyle. This is substantiated by the fact that urban areas have a higher incidence than rural areas, and High socio-economic classes. It is idiopathic in nature, but there are diet, drugs and stress. It is the result of an abnormal response by body's immune system. According to Ayurveda, vitiated Pitta and Rakta are responsible for inflammation and ulceration[2] The symptoms of ulcerative colitis can be co-related with Pittaja Grahani [3] . According to Ayurvedic classics, people with Pittaja Grahani have tendency to develop Raktatisara when they do not follow Pathya ahara and Vihara. Again, consumption of hot, spicy and fried food along with stress, anxiety etc leads to Raktatisara. Therefore, the first line of treatment is Nidana parivarjana followed by use of Sansamana Chikitsa like Rakta stambhaka (blood coagulatory) and Purisha Sanghrahi i.e., anti- diarrheal medicines. To measure to digest the Ama (bio toxin) to bring Agni (digestive fire) in its normal state and control the diarrhea and get the restoring health digestion and creating a bacteria friendly environment in the body and relief in all other complaints.

2. Case Study

A diagnosed patient of Ulcerative colitis, age 14yrs male from Khushinagar Gorakhpur, came to OPD of Kayachikitsa Guru Gorakshnath institute of medical sciences Gorakhpur. He complained bleeding per rectum, Stools with blood during

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defecation. Associated with fresh bleeding after defecation, since 8 months, weight loss 6-7 kgs in 6 months, mild intermittent abdominal pain, associated with bloating off and on, Fever off and on, His report of colonoscopy biopsy from rectum shows crypt architectural distortion, crypt shortening with inflammatory expansion of the lamina propria with basal lymph plasmacytosis. Cryptitis and crypt abscess are also seen. Thin caliber blood vessels granulation tissue and hemorrhage also seen in background [Fig no: 1]. and sigmoidoscopy shows proctitis, loss of vascular pattern, multiple small ulcerations [Fig No: 2]. other hematological parameters were normal, renal parameters and blood sugar also within normal limits. Stool examination occult blood present.

2.1. General Examination

- No pallor, clubbing cyanosis found
- Weight-62.8 kg
- BP-110/90 mmhg
- Pulse-81 Beat per min.
- Resp-20/M
- Spo2-98@RA.
- Lymph nodes are not palpable.

2.2. Systemic Examination

- CVS- S1 & S2 Heard, no abnormality detected in cardiovascular system
- RS - B/L air entry normal
- CNS- conscious and oriented with date, time & place
- P/A-Mild abdominal tenderness @ umbilical region, no organomegaly
- P/R- no piles mass present
- Auscultation- 9 bowel sounds/minute.

In Ayurveda, the ancient system of India medicine, is mainly based on the concept of Dosha and Dushya. Due to sedentary life style, faulty food habit, stressful working nature, Pitta dosha aggravated diet intake finally led to suppression of Agni (Digestive fire) which are mentioned as root cause of Pittja Grahani which in chronic stage manifest as Raktatisara.

Diagnostic Features of Grahani:[4]

Nidan panchaka

Nidan of Grahani Roga:

Aharaja, abhojana, vishamashana, asatmya, guru, sheeta, atirooksha, bhojana, Viharaja-vega nigraha, karshana due to vyadhi.

Panchakarma vibrama-virechana, vamana and snehavibhrama.

- Abstinence from food (Abhojana)
- Indigestion (Ajirna)
- Over-eating (Atibhojana)
- Ingestion of -
 - Unwholesome food (Asatmya bhojana)
 - Heavy or indigestible food (Atiguru bho- jana)
 - Cold and food (Shita bhojana)
 - Excessively dry and dehydrated food (Ati- rukshabhojana)
 - Putridarticle (Sandusta bhojana)
- Adverse effects of the therapeutic measures such as, Purgation, Emesis, Oleation
- Emaciation or wasting brought about by other diseases
- Incompatibility of the – country, climate, season
- Voluntary inhibition of natural urges (Vega grahani).

2.3. Types of Grahani roga

Grahani is of 4 types according to Charaka, Sushruta, Vagbhata.

2.3.1. Vataja grahani samprapti

Due to consumption of Vataja ahara vihara vata gets aggravated and covers the suppressed agni (power of digestion). As a result of this, the food taken by the patient does not get easily digested which leads vataja grahani .

2.3.2. Pittaja grahani

Due to pittaja ahara vihara pitta gets vitiated leads to aaplavana of Agni and leads to pittaja grahani. Aaplavana means- aaplaavayadyan-thaanalamithi- it destroys Agni, aaplavanam-dravenaardrikanam-dravata vriddi of pitta leads ardrikanam of agni, like water kindles fire.

2.3.3. Kaphaja grahani

Due to kaphakara ahara vihara kapha get vitiated leads to indigestion of food leads to kaphaja grahani.

2.3.4. Sannipataja grahani

Sannipataja grahani is to be determined on the basis of simultaneous manifestation of all the signs symptoms pertaining to the three dosas.

2.3.5. Poorvaroopa of Grahani

Thrishna(theist),Aalasya(laziness),Balakshaya(Generalised weakness),Vidaha(burning sensation during digestion of food),Chirapaka(delayed digestion),Kayagauravam(heaviness of the body).

2.3.6. Lakshana of Grahani

Pittaja Grahani

Specific character- Foetid and sour eructation

Generalised symptoms- Roughness in body,dryness of throat, mouth.Hunger, thirst, blurred vision, tinnitus, pain in chest,thigh, pelvic, neck region, weakness, Parikartika,cough, dyspnoea

Character of stool- Watery, undigested, yellowish stool.

2.4. Samprapti Ghataka

- Dosa : Pitta pradhana tridoshaja (Vata-samana vata,pitta- Pachaka,Kapha-Kledaka)
- Dusya : Rasa ,Rakta
- Agni :Jatharagni
- Agni dusti : Mandagni
- Ama :Agnijanya
- Srotas :Anna vaha
- Srotodusti :Sang,Vimarg gamana,
- Adhistana :Grahani
- Udbhavasthana :Grahani
- Vyaktastha :Grahani
- Sancharasthan :Maha srotas,Annavaaha srotas
- Sadhya-Asadyata :Krachasadhya

2.5. Treatment

2.5.1. Shodhana therapy

For Shodhana therapy anuvasana basti & ksheera basti[5] was given for 15 days in three session with two intervals, the following table no: 1, 2 & 3 shows the treatment.

Table 1 1st Session of Shodhana chikitsa

Days	Shodana Chikitsa
1 st day	Jatyadi tala matra basti- 40ml
2 nd day	Jatyadi taila Yashtimadhu ksheera basti
3 rd day	Jatyadi taila matra basti- 60ml
4 th day	Jatyadi taila matra basti- 80ml
5 th day	Jatyadi taila matra basti- 80ml

Table 2 2nd Session of Shodhana chikitsa

Days	Shodhana Chikitsa
1 st day	Murivenna taila yastimadhu ksheera basti
2 nd day	Murivenna taila yastimadhu ksheera basti
3 rd day	Murivenna taila yastimadhu ksheera basti
4 th day	Murivenna taila yastimadhu ksheera basti
5 th day	Murivenna taila yastimadhu ksheera basti

Table 3 3rd Session of Shodhana chikitsa

Days	Shodhana Chikitsa
1 st day	Murivenna taila yastimadhu ksheera basti
2 nd day	Murivenna taila yastimadhu ksheera basti
3 rd day	Murivenna taila yastimadhu ksheera basti
4 th day	Murivenna taila yastimadhu ksheera basti
5 th day	Murivenna taila matra basti -70ml

2.5.2. Shamana therapy

Following combination, the drug had been used as follow and changed according to response of the disease. Internal medicine was given continuously for 2 months. Table no:4

Table 4 Shamana chikitsa

S. No	Aushadhi	Matra	Anupana	Time and duration	Days
1	Kutaja parpati	2	water	TID	1 month
2	Kutaja ghanavati	2	water	TID	1 month
3	Lakshadi churna	5 gm	Luke warm water	BD	1 month
4	Usheerasava	40ml	water	TID	2 months
5	Lakshadi guggulu	2	Luke warm water	BD	1 month
6	Pushyanuga churna	15gm	water	BD	1 month
7	Shimshapa patra churna	15gm	Mishri	BD	10 days

2.6. Result and Interpretation

Patients continued treatment for 1 month. All the signs and symptoms of Ulcerative colitis completely relieved in after 1 month and bleeding during and after defecation has been stopped completely.

2.7. Symptoms before and after treatment

2.7.1. Ayurvedic perspective

Acharya Vagbhatta described Mandagni refers to diminished digestive fire or diminished enzymatic activities of our body. Acharya Charaka has described digestive system as Mahasrotas. While Acharya Sushruta described as Annavaha srotas and Purishavaha Srotas in which these diseases like Pittaja Grahani, Raktatisara, Raktaja Arsh, Raktaja Pravahika occurs, which alone or as a complication produces ulcerative colitis like symptoms. Yasthimadhu having Rakta-pittashamaka, Varano-ropaka, Stambhaka properties. It activates ulcer healing vatapitta hara, Madhura guru guna & snigdha properties of yastimadhu pacifies pitta & it helps in healing ulcers.

Observation

Based on the bleeding per rectum the progress of the treatment was achieved. Patient on his first consultation in our hospital reported 9-10ml bleeding per rectum during and after defecation which gradually reduced during the treatment. The following table shows the treatment progress.

Table 5 Treatment progress

Sl. No	No: of days	Bleeding per rectum
First session	5 days	10ml – 5 ml ↓
Second session	5 days	3ml- 0.5, 1ml ↓
Third session	5 days	0.5ml – 1.5ml ↑

After three sessions of treatments patient was advised for internal medications for one month and also advised to reduce intake of salt, investigation were done. Histopathology report shows there is multiple mucosal pieces exhibiting surface epithelium, lamina propria with muscularis mucosa, glands are lined by tall columnar epithelium dense chronic inflammatory cells infiltrate seen in lamina propria with occasional polymorphs, cryptitis is noted. There is no findings of crypt architectural distortion, there is no plasmacytosis of basal lymph in lamina propria. Crypt abscess are also not seen. Thin caliber blood vessels granulation tissue and hemorrhage also not seen in background [Fig No: 3].

Sigmoidoscopy shows there is diffuse erosion, erythema, mucosal edema, sloughing seen in rectum. There is no proctitis, loss of vascular pattern, multiple small ulcerations. it is reduced to diffuse erosion, erythema, mucosal edema, sloughing seen in rectum [Fig No: 4].

Other hematological parameters were normal, renal parameters and blood sugar also within normal limits [Fig No: 5].

3. Discussion

As per presentation of disease is progressive disorder of unknown etiology on the basis of sign and symptoms that diagnosed as Ulcerative colitis correlated with Pittaja Grahani. The disease Ulcerative colitis is not curable as we know well, but we can improve the life span and quality of life of the patient. Here some of the preparation selected on the basis of involvement of Doshas, Dushya of the disease. All the treatment of Ayurevda formulations mainly Rakta Pitta

Shamaka, Deepana & Grahi are in nature.

Kutaja parpati [8]: it balances vata pitta and kapha, it is indicated in malabsorption syndrome, diarrhea, and intestinal ulcers.

Kutaja ghana vati [9]: it balances vata and pitta, it is used in treating diarrhea, dysentery, ulcerative colitis, malabsorption syndrome.

Lakshadi churna [10]: it is effective herbal powder to treat the bleeding disorders. It is used to treat the various problems like nasal bleeding, heavy periods, hemoptysis etc (B.R 27/13)

Ushirasava[11]: it is liquid form of medicine used in treatment of bleeding disorders like rectal bleeding, menorrhagia epistaxis etc, skin diseases, blood purification and urinary problems etc. this is cooling in nature and pacifies excess pitta dosha in body.

Pushyanuga churna [12]: (Cha. Chi 30/90-96, B.R Strirogadhikara 46-49): Pushyanuga churna is an eminent Ayurvedic medicine, in the form of herbal powder that can soothe Vata, Pitta and Kapha. It is kasahya(astringent), katu(pungent), Madhura(sweet) and tikta(bitter) In taste. It acts on plasma, blood, muscles and reproductive system. This is very useful in bleeding disorders.

Shisham patra churna [12]: it is used for the treatment of vitiligo, fever non healing wounds, ulcers, and intestinal parasites. It pacifies all three doshas.

Ksheera Basti has a definitive role in the management of pittaja grahani. Here Pitta shamaka dravya (styptic drugs) are used for the preparation of the ksheera Basti. Because of this property it has ulcer healing effect. Actions of

Ksheera Basti [16] are - Shothahara and Vrana-Ropaka (anti-inflammatory and ulcer-healing), Rakta-stambhaka (haemostatic agent), Sangrahi (anti-diarrhoeal), Pitta Shamaka. Ingredients of Ksheera basti Yasthimadhu [13] having Rakta-pittashamaka, Varano-ropaka, Stambhaka properties. It activates ulcer healing vatapitta hara, Madhura guru guna & snigdha properties of yasthimadhu pacifies pitta & it helps in healing ulcers

4. Conclusion

Matra vasti and Ksheera vasti with medicated drugs not only reduces the complications and also fully stopped the per rectal bleeding completely, symptoms of the disease but also inhibit relapses or re-occurrence of the disease.

Figure 1 Colonoscopy Biopsy reports before treatment

Figure 2 Sigmoidoscopy reports before treatment

Figure 3 Histopathology reports after treatment

Figure 4 Sigmoidoscopy reports after treatment

Figure 5 Hematological parameters after treatment

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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